

MICROBIOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT OF OPENED SOFT DRINK BOTTLES FOR PATHOGENIC BACTERIA ASSOCIATED WITH DRINKING DIRECTLY FROM THE ORIFICE.

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ABSTRACT

Four types of carbonated soft drinks encoded as A, B, C and D; and bottled and sealed water E (used as control) were bought from a student restaurant in the Rivers State University of Science and Technology, Port Harcourt Nigeria. The area of the orifice and neck of the bottles usually placed in the mouth while drinking directly from the bottles was analyzed in triplicates for the impinging bacterial species. Of the eighty-three morphologically identified aerobic isolates the percent frequency of occurrence was: *Staphylococcus aureus* (38.4%), *Bacillus* and other gram-positive rods (36.0 %), *Enterococcus* sp (12.0 %), *Micrococcus* spp (8.4% each), and *Proteus* and *Pseudomonas* spp (2.4% each). The Standard Plate Count expressed as the Colony Forming Units (CFU) indicated a range of 5.3×10^3 to $2.6.0 \times 10^4$ CFU ml⁻¹ of the rinsate of the orifice and neck of the soft-drink bottles. The preponderance of the indicator organisms: Coagulase positive *S. aureus* and the *Enterococci* sp is used to infer the presence of potentially pathogenic bacteria. The need for public health enlightenment on the packaging and safe conduits for the distribution of soft drinks was discussed.

KEY WORDS: Soft drink, bottles, enumeration, pathogenic bacteria, orifice, public health

INTRODUCTION

Soft-drinks

Soft drinks are defined as bottled or canned non-alcoholic, carbonated or non-carbonated, flavored beverages that are usually served cold (Hoffmann *et al.*, 1997). They vary in composition including: lemon, orange, lime, assorted fruit-juices, colas, ginger ales, sodas, root beers (CSDA, 1996). There are few published works on the health risk, especially in the Third World, that could arise from the consumption of soft drinks directly from the orifice of the opened bottles. Hoffmann *et al.*, (1997), carried out the microbiological survey of non-alcoholic carbonated beverages while Griffiths *et al.*, (1997) carried out an analysis of the quality of the ingredients used in the Soft-drink Industries. In 2005, Amusa *et al* carried out studies on the microbiological and nutritional quality of a hawked locally brewed soft drink called *zobo* in Nigeria, while Oranusi *et al*, 1994, studied the microbial contaminants of commercially bottled non-alcoholic drinks produced in Nigeria.

Consumption of soft drinks

The consumption of soft drinks is a worldwide phenomenon as they serve as a means of quenching thirst and for energy. Especially in the Third World with its food shortages and scarce clean water for drinking, children and the working class consume much soft drink almost on daily basis especially in the rush hours. There is suspected negligence by all concerned in the sanitary handling of soft drinks as expected in the food industry. Unfortunately, advertisements show pictures of individuals relishing soft drinks while drinking directly from the opened bottles; this appears to be copied especially by the youths. Crates of soft-drink bottles could be found stacked exposed to all conceivable environmental conditions: on the bare soil and dust, close to gutters, in the rain, behind premises a times close to conveniences. Furthermore, bottles of soft-drinks are very often sold without washing at all or where washing was done, it was with rain water, well-water or very rarely with tap-water.

There is a probable lack of or non-conformity with appropriate legislation as regards bottling and packaging of soft drinks for consumption by the generality of the populace by the bottling companies. The practice of selling soft drinks in capped glass-bottles (which are returned to the bottling companies for a deposit amount) especially in the rural areas has continued for decades. It is suspected that in a bid to sell soft drinks at cheaper rates to a greater number in the society, sanitary standards have been overlooked. In more organized

establishments like most standard hotels, soft drinks could be dispensed from tanks directly into washed drinking-glasses or sold from disposable and sealed plastic bottles though at a higher price.

Survival of microorganisms in harsh environments

Microorganisms especially bacteria are known for their ability to survive in different environments such as on soil, air, water and foods. They are also known to survive on a number of materials which are depleted in nutrients and moisture that are used by man such as clothing, catheters and glassware (Pelczar *et al*, 1988). Schmidt-Lorenz, 1978, observed that microorganisms, which have simple nutritional requirements such as *Flavobacterium* species and *Pseudomonads*, could multiply in stored spring and mineral water at room temperature. Coliform bacteria have been known to occur in chlorinated drinking water supply (Hudson *et al*, 1983). Lechevallier *et al*, 1984, showed that attached bacteria grown in a low nutrient medium exhibited more resistance to harsh conditions and antibiotics than unattached bacterial grown in a rich medium. There is therefore the likelihood of bacteria that are hardy to desiccation and antibiotics surviving on the orifice and neck of bottles of soft drinks. The type of microflora found on the hands, arms, nasal cavities, mouth or garments of food handlers, which are picked up from dust, water, soil etc, to a great extent reflect the sanitary state of food handlers. The most common bacteria that are transmitted from food handlers include the Genera *Micrococcus* and *Staphylococcus* (Jay, 1987).

Pathogenicity of microorganisms

Microorganisms are able to cause disease when they gain access to the host, adhere to host tissue, penetrate host defenses and damage host tissue. Among the known hardy organisms that occur under very harsh environmental conditions, which are capable of causing disease in man, include *Bacillus* sp, *Staphylococcus* sp and the *Enterococcus* sp (Tortora *et al*, 1992; Murray, 1990).

Bacillus species are among some of the most virulent and destructive pathogens. Food-poisoning outbreaks attributable to *Bacillus cereus* have been known since 1906 (Logan, 1988). The *Staphylococcus* species as described by Jawetz *et al*, (1978), are members of the normal flora of the human skin and of the respiratory and gastrointestinal tracts. They are also found in the air and human environments. The pathogenic capacity of a given strain of *Staphylococcus* species depends on the presence of the extracellular factors and toxins together with the invasive properties. J. Denys first studied staphylococcus food poisoning in 1894. The capacity of some strains of *S. aureus* to cause food poisoning was proved conclusively by Dack *et al*, 1930. Food poisoning is often produced mainly by strains that produce coagulase. All symptoms of *Staphylococcus* gastroenteritis are caused by the extracellular enterotoxins (Jay, 1987). The presence of large numbers of *S. aureus* in foods therefore is an indication of much handling of such foods by man.

Other Gram-positive bacteria that are encountered in handling and environmental infestation of foods include the *Micrococcus* and *Enterococcus* spp. The *Enterococcus* sp in particular has been associated in recent times with nosocomial infections and is the subject of much investigation as agents of cross drug-resistance transmission among the gram-positive cocci (Murray, 1990). The Gram-negative bacteria are indicative of probable faecal contamination and include the *Alcagenes*, *Pseudomonas*, *Escherichia coli*, *Serratia* and *Proteus* and the *Proteus* (Jay, 1987).

The aim of the study is therefore to assess the microbial load and frequency of occurrence of indicator pathogenic bacterial species that could be acquired from the orifice and neck of the opened soft drink bottles while drinking directly from the orifice.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample collection and treatment

Four different brands of soft drinks encoded as (A, B, C, D); and bottled and sealed water (E); were bought from the Student Restaurant, Rivers State University of Science and Technology, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The samples (in triplicates) were taken to the laboratory within one hour after purchase and stored in the refrigerator at 5°C prior to analysis. Each bottle of drink was carefully emptied of its content to avoid spillage on the outer surface of the bottle. The bacterial isolates on the orifice and neck (~ 2.5 cm in length) of the bottles were obtained by rinsing them separately in sterilized 20 ml of nutrient broth in sterile beakers. The rinsates were incubated for 6h at 37 °C for the resuscitation of the dormant forms. CFU ml⁻¹ was determined as the Standard Plate Count (SPC) from the rinsate of the area of the orifice and neck of the bottles. Only plate counts of 30-300 ml⁻¹ of rinsates

were counted. The area of the orifice and neck of the bottles were determined by wrapping aluminium foil around them and then measuring of the area of the aluminium foil for each type of drink.

All media, unless otherwise stated were autoclaved at 121°C for 15 min.

The nutrient agar (NA), MacConkey agar (MCA), normal saline, sugars and Mannitol Salt Agar (MSA) were prepared in Petri dishes, as slants and as broth according to manufacturer's specifications.

Characterization and identification of isolates.

Inoculation of both the NA and MCA plates was carried-out using the activated rinsates. 0.1 ml of each rinsate was pipetted onto plates of NA, MSA and MCA and spread using a sterile glass-spreader. The plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24h. Morphologically different colonies were subcultured. Characterization and identification was carried out using cultural morphology variation, Gram's reaction, and biochemical tests (including MSA, Coagulase tests, Catalase, Litmus-Milk de-coloration and sugar-utilization) according to the procedure for specific organisms as shown in Cheesbrough, (1984).

RESULTS

The consumption pattern of drinking by consumers of soft-drinks in the Rivers State University of Science and Technology Students' Restaurant indicated that over 95% of students drank the soft-drinks directly from the orifice of the bottles while less than 5% were safety conscious and poured their drinks into cups or used drinking straws for drinking.

Table 1, showed the tentatively identified aerobic bacterial isolates from the soft drink bottles. Three of the most frequently isolated bacterial forms were gram positive cocci and included *S. aureus*, the *Enterococcus* and the *Micrococcus*; two of the isolates were gram negative rods viz. the *Proteus* and *Pseudomonas* spp and also identified were the *Bacillus* and other gram positive rods. The bottled water indicated the presence of *S.aureus* and *Bacillus* and other gram positive rods which appear to be laboratory contaminants.

In Fig 1, the occurrence of the different bacterial isolates showed that coagulase positive *S. aureus* (5-11 CFU cm⁻²) had the highest frequency of occurrence of isolates from the orifice and neck of the soft drink bottles; while for the bottled and sealed water coagulase negative *S. aureus* count was only 2 CFU cm⁻². The *Bacillus* sp and other Gram positive bacteria indicated a frequency of 1-9 CFU cm⁻² and occurred on the orifice and neck of both the soft-drinks and the bottled and sealed water sample. The *Enterococcus* sp occurred only on the soft-drink bottles indicating a range of 1-5 CFU cm⁻². *Bacillus* sp often occurred as laboratory contaminants.

In Fig 2, the CFU cm⁻² of the orifice and neck of the soft-drink bottles indicated microbial load ranging from 5 x 10³-2.6 x 10⁴ cm⁻²; while for the bottled water this was less than 3 x 10⁰ cm⁻². The cumulative frequency of isolation of each bacterial species from the orifice and neck of the soft-drink bottles (as shown in Fig 3) indicated a percent frequency of isolation of *Staphylococcus aureus* of (38.4%), these were tube and/or slide coagulase positive. These were the most frequently isolated; this was followed by the *Bacillus* spp and other gram-positive rods (36.0%); the *Enterococci* sp (12.0%); the *Micrococcus* sp (each 8.4 %); and *Proteus* and *Pseudomonas* spp were each 2.4 %.

DISCUSSION

Sokari and Kigigha (1998) had indicated the probable incidence of microbiological health risk arising from environmental contamination in medicine dispensing bottles in Port Harcourt metropolis. The study showed that medicine dispensing bottles were either not washed at all or only sparingly so with water of doubtful quality; in which frequency of characterized bacterial species was *Bacillus* and other gram-positive spp (4.9%); *S.aureus* (18.2%); *Staphylococcus spp* (13.3%) etc. Other identified forms were the *Enterococcus* sp; the *Proteus* sp and the *Pseudomonas* sp; these bacterial forms were also identified in the present study.

There is a correlation between coagulase production and ability to cause infection especially in food poisoning outbreaks in *S. aureus* (Tortora *et al*, 1992). There was over 38 % frequency of occurrence of coagulase positive *S. aureus* in this study. Moreover the occurrence of 11% frequency of occurrence of *Enterococcus* sp indicated a serious health implication. The *Enterococcus* sp is known to survive under very harsh environmental conditions and are intrinsically resistant to a number of antibiotics (Murray, 1990). The ability to exchange genetic elements for drug-resistance through transposons freely with other gram-positive cocci indicated that the

Enterococcus sp were a serious threat to human health in terms of nosocomial infections transmission, prophylaxis and therapy in this era of massive use of antibiotics (Kogstad *et al* 1976; Clewell, 1981).

There was an indication that the capped and sealed bottled water was not contaminated from the environmental sources especially as coagulase positive *S.aureus* and *Enterococcus* sp were absent. For the control of hazardous bacterial forms there is the need for appropriate legislation and enforcement on use of sealed simple disposable plastic bottles or foil covered tops for the soft drinks. Also recommended is the packaging of soft drinks in plastic sealed crates and the outright abolishing of the practice of returning glass bottles for refundable deposits to the Bottling Companies especially in the rural areas.

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Table 1: Characteristics of bacteria isolated from the orifice and neck of Bottles.

Tests and Assessments	Isolates					
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI
Colonial morphology	Creamy Entire	Whitish/dry Entire	Golden Entire	Mucoid Entire	Creamy Entire	Mucoid Entire
Gram's reaction	+ve cocci	+ve rods	+ve cocci	- ve rods	+ve cocci	- ve rods
Growth on MSA	In chains	in chains	in clusters			
Tube coagulase	- ve	NT	+ve	NT	+ve	NT
Slide coagulase	- ve	NT	+ve	NT	- ve	NT
Litmus decolorization	- ve	NT	+ ve	NT	- ve	NT
Oxidase	+ve	NT	-ve	NT	- ve	NT
Sugar utilization:	NT	NT	NT	- ve	NT	+ve
Lactose	NT	NT	NT	- ve	NT	- ve
Mannitol				- ve		- ve
Glucose				+ve		- ve
Sucrose				+ve		- ve
Tentative Isolate Identification	<i>Enterococcus</i> Sp	<i>Bacillus</i> sp & other rods	<i>S. aureus</i> **	<i>Proteus</i> sp	<i>Micrococcus</i> spp	<i>Pseudomonas</i> spp
CFU cm ⁻² from orifice & neck of Bottles						
A.....	2	5	8	1	2	2
B.....	1	8	7	0	4	0
C.....	5	10	4	1	0	0
D.....	2	6	11	0	1	0
E.....	0	1	2	0	0	0
Cumulative CFU Cm ² Neck Soft drink bottles	10	30	32	2	6	2
Frequency of Isolation Of bacteria from bottles						
A.....	2 (10.0)*	5 (25.0)	8 (40.0)	1 (5.0)	2 (10.0)	2 (10.0)
B.....	1 (5)	8 (40.0)	7 (35.0)	0	4 (20.0)	0
C.....	5 (25.0)	10 (50)	4 (20.0)	1 (5)	0	0
D.....	2 (10.0)	6 (30.0)	11(55.0)	0	1 (5)	0
E.....	0	1 (33.3)	2 (66.6)	0	0	0
Cumulative Frequency of bacterial isolations from neck of bottles	10 (12.0)	30 (36.0)	32 (38.4)	2 (2.4)	7 (8.4)	2 (2.4)

SPC were averages of three plate counts; * Numbers in parenthesis represent percentages; ** *S. aureus* were tube and /or slide coagulase positive; NT: Not tested

Key
 I.....*Enterococcus* sp; II.....*Bacillus* & other Gram +ve rods; III.....*S.aureus*; IV.....*Proteus* sp
 V.....*Micrococcus* sp; VI.....*Pseudomonas* sp; A, B, C, DSoft-drinks; E.....Sealed and bottled water
 Fig 1. Frequency of isolation of bacterial forms from soft-drink bottles.

Key
 A, B, C, DSoft-drinks; E.....Sealed and bottled water

Fig 2. Bacterial load per ml of rinsate of the area placed in the mouth while drinking soft-drinks.

Key
 I.....*Enterococcus* sp; II.....*Bacillus* & other Gram +ve rods; III.....*S.aureus*; IV.....*Proteus* sp
 V.....*Micrococcus* sp; VI.....*Pseudomonas* sp.

Fig 3. Cumulative frequency of isolation of bacterial forms from soft-drink bottles.

Received for Publication: 10/01/12

Accepted for Publication: 11/04/12

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